

Logarithm of the ratio of two independent beta random variables

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In this document, I show that the density of $Z = \ln X_1/X_2$ with $X_1 \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_1, \beta_1)$ and $X_2 \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_2, \beta_2)$ two independent beta random variables is given by:

$$f_Z(z) = \begin{cases} \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2} B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2, \beta_1)}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1) B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} F(1 - \beta_2, \alpha_1 + \alpha_2; \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \beta_1; e^{-z}), & z > 0 \\ \frac{e^{z\alpha_1} B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2, \beta_2)}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1) B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} F(1 - \beta_1, \alpha_1 + \alpha_2; \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \beta_2; e^z), & z \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

where F is the hypergeometric series. I derive the moments of order n and I use these results to describe the density of Relative Risk under the null hypothesis. I also present a script in Octave that plots the density of Z and compares it with a randomly generated distribution, among other things.

1 Density

PROP. 1 (lemma). Given $X \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta)$ let us consider the random variable $Y = \ln X$. The probability density is

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad f_Y(y) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} e^{y\alpha} (1 - e^y)^{\beta-1}, & y \leq 0 \\ 0, & y > 0 \end{cases}$$

Proof. If we indicate F_Y, F_X the cumulative distribution function of Y and X respectively, we have

$$\begin{aligned} F_Y(y) &= P(Y \leq y) = P(\ln X \leq y) = P(X \leq e^y) = F_X(x = e^y) \Rightarrow \\ &\Rightarrow f_Y(y) = \frac{dF_X(x)}{dx} \frac{de^y}{dx} = \frac{dF_X(x)}{dx} e^y = f_X(e^y) e^y \end{aligned}$$

Since $f_X(e^y) = \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} e^{y(\alpha-1)} (1 - e^y)^{\beta-1}$ the proof is concluded ■

PROP. 2 (lemma). Given $X \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta)$ let us consider the random variable $Z = -\ln X$. The probability density is

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad f_Z(z) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} e^{-z\alpha} (1 - e^{-z})^{\beta-1}, & z \geq 0 \\ 0, & z < 0 \end{cases}$$

Proof. We reason as in the previous proof:

$$\begin{aligned} F_Z(z) &= P(Z \leq z) = P\left(\ln \frac{1}{X} \leq z\right) = P\left(\frac{1}{X} \leq e^{-z}\right) = P(X \geq e^{-z}) = 1 - F_X(x = e^{-z}) \Rightarrow \\ &\Rightarrow f_Z(z) = -\frac{dF_X(x)}{dx} \frac{de^{-z}}{dx} = \frac{dF_X(x)}{dx} e^{-z} = f_X(e^{-z}) e^{-z} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore we have $f_Z(z) = \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} e^{-z(\alpha-1)} (1 - e^{-z})^{\beta-1} e^{-z} = \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} e^{-z\alpha} (1 - e^{-z})^{\beta-1}$ ■

PROP. 3 (density). Assigned the two independent random variables $X_1 \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_1, \beta_1)$ and $X_2 \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_2, \beta_2)$ let us consider the $Z = \ln X_1/X_2$. Its density is given by:

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad f_Z(z) = \begin{cases} \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_2 - 1}{k} (-1)^k e^{-kz} B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + k, \beta_1), & z > 0 \\ \frac{e^{z\alpha_1}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_1 - 1}{k} (-1)^k e^{kz} B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + k, \beta_2), & z \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

Proof. We have $Z = \ln X_1/X_2 = \ln X_1 - \ln X_2$. Assigned $Y_1 = \ln X_1, Y_2 = -\ln X_2$ we can write $Z = Y_1 + Y_2$, therefore we have:

$$f_Z(z) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f_Y(y_1, z - y_1) dy_1 = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f_{Y_1}(y_1) f_{Y_2}(z - y_1) dy_1$$

From PROP. 1 and PROP. 2 we find

$$f_{Y_1}(y_1) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)} e^{y_1\alpha_1} (1 - e^{y_1})^{\beta_1-1}, & y_1 \leq 0 \\ 0, & y_1 > 0 \end{cases}$$

$$f_{Y_2}(z - y_1) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} e^{-(z-y_1)\alpha_2} (1 - e^{-(z-y_1)})^{\beta_2-1}, & y_1 \leq z \\ 0, & y_1 > z \end{cases}$$

It follows that the density of Z has an expression for $z > 0$ and another for $z \leq 0$. In fact, we have

$$f_Z(z) = \begin{cases} \int_{-\infty}^0 f_{Y_1}(y_1) f_{Y_2}(z - y_1) dy_1, & z > 0 \\ \int_{-\infty}^z f_{Y_1}(y_1) f_{Y_2}(z - y_1) dy_1, & z \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

Moreover, the integrand can be written

$$f_{Y_1}(y_1) f_{Y_2}(z - y_1) = \frac{1}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} e^{-z\alpha_2 + y_1(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)} (1 - e^{-(z-y_1)})^{\beta_2-1} (1 - e^{y_1})^{\beta_1-1}$$

Hence, for $z > 0$ we have

$$f_Z(z) = \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \int_{-\infty}^0 e^{y_1(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)} (1 - e^{-z} e^{y_1})^{\beta_2-1} (1 - e^{y_1})^{\beta_1-1} dy_1$$

We now consider the substitution $e^{y_1} = t \Leftrightarrow y_1 = \ln t$ and we have:

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad f_Z(z) = \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \int_0^1 t^{(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 1)} (1 - e^{-z} t)^{\beta_2-1} (1 - t)^{\beta_1-1} dt, \quad z > 0$$

Since $z > 0$, it follows $e^{-z}t \leq t$, therefore we can consider the convergent series $(1 - e^{-z}t)^{\beta_2-1} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_2-1}{k} (-1)^k e^{-kz} t^k$ and by integration by series, we have

$$f_Z(z) = \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_2-1}{k} (-1)^k e^{-kz} \int_0^1 t^{(\alpha_1+\alpha_2+k-1)} (1-t)^{\beta_1-1} dt \Rightarrow$$

$$f_Z(z) = \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_2-1}{k} (-1)^k e^{-kz} B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + k, \beta_1), \quad z > 0$$

When $z \leq 0$, the substitution $e^{y_1} = t$ gives

$$f_Z(z) = \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \int_{-\infty}^z e^{-z\alpha_2+y_1(\alpha_1+\alpha_2)} (1 - e^{-(z-y_1)})^{\beta_2-1} (1 - e^{y_1})^{\beta_1-1} dy_1 \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad f_Z(z) = \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \int_0^{e^z} t^{(\alpha_1+\alpha_2-1)} (1 - e^{-z}t)^{\beta_2-1} (1 - t)^{\beta_1-1} dt$$

Note now that $0 \leq t \leq e^z < 1$, therefore $(1 - t)^{\beta_1-1} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_1-1}{k} (-1)^k t^k$ and we can integrate by series again:

$$f_Z(z) = \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_1-1}{k} (-1)^k \int_0^{e^z} t^{(\alpha_1+\alpha_2+k-1)} (1 - e^{-z}t)^{\beta_2-1} dt =$$

$$= \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2} e^z e^{z(\alpha_1+\alpha_2-1)}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_1-1}{k} e^{zk} (-1)^k \int_0^{e^z} (e^{-z}t)^{(\alpha_1+\alpha_2+k-1)} (1 - e^{-z}t)^{\beta_2-1} d(e^{-z}t) =$$

$$= \frac{e^{z\alpha_1}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_1-1}{k} e^{zk} (-1)^k \int_0^1 \xi^{(\alpha_1+\alpha_2+k-1)} (1 - \xi)^{\beta_2-1} d\xi =$$

$$= \frac{e^{z\alpha_1}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_1-1}{k} e^{zk} (-1)^k B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + k, \beta_2)$$

And the proof is complete ■

PROP. 4 (alternative expression). The density in PROP. 3 can be written equivalently as follows:

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad f_Z(z) = \begin{cases} \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2} B(\alpha_1+\alpha_2, \beta_1)}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} F(1 - \beta_2, \alpha_1 + \alpha_2; \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \beta_1; e^{-z}), & z > 0 \\ \frac{e^{z\alpha_1} B(\alpha_1+\alpha_2, \beta_2)}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} F(1 - \beta_1, \alpha_1 + \alpha_2; \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \beta_2; e^z), & z \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

where we have considered the integral formulation of the hypergeometric series:

$$F(a, b; c; x) = \frac{1}{B(b, c-b)} \int_0^1 t^{b-1} (1-t)^{c-b-1} (1-tx)^{-a} dt$$

Figure 1. Densities of $Y = \ln X_1, Y = \ln X_2^{-1}, Z = \ln \frac{X_1}{X_2}$ for $X_1 \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_1, \beta_1), X_2 \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_2, \beta_2)$. The histograms from randomly generated distributions are also reported.

Proof. From the definition of the hypergeometric series we have:

$$\begin{aligned} F(1 - \beta_2, \alpha_1 + \alpha_2; \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \beta_1; e^{-z}) &= \\ &= \frac{1}{B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2, \beta_1)} \int_0^1 t^{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 1} (1-t)^{\beta_1 - 1} (1-te^{-z})^{\beta_2 - 1} dt \end{aligned}$$

It follows that Eq. 4 can be written

$$\begin{aligned} f_Z(z) &= \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \int_0^1 t^{(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 1)} (1 - e^{-z}t)^{\beta_2 - 1} (1-t)^{\beta_1 - 1} dt = \\ &= \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2} B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2, \beta_1)}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} F(1 - \beta_2, \alpha_1 + \alpha_2; \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \beta_1; e^{-z}), \quad z > 0 \end{aligned}$$

From the definition of the hypergeometric series, we also have

$$\begin{aligned} F(1 - \beta_1, \alpha_1 + \alpha_2; \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \beta_2; e^z) &= \\ &= \frac{1}{B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2, \beta_2)} \int_0^1 t^{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 1} (1-t)^{\beta_2 - 1} (1 - e^z t)^{\beta_1 - 1} dt \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, from Eq. 5 it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} f_Z(z) &= \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \int_0^{e^z} t^{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 1} (1-t)^{\beta_1 - 1} (1 - e^{-z}t)^{\beta_2 - 1} dt = \\ &= \frac{e^{-z\alpha_2} e^z e^{z(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 1)}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \int_0^{e^z} (e^{-z}t)^{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 1} (1-t)^{\beta_1 - 1} (1 - e^{-z}t)^{\beta_2 - 1} d(e^{-z}t) = \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{e^{z\alpha_1}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \int_0^1 \xi^{\alpha_1+\alpha_2-1} (1-\xi)^{\beta_2-1} (1-\xi e^z)^{\beta_1-1} d\xi = \\
&= \frac{e^{z\alpha_1} B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2, \beta_2)}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} F(1 - \beta_1, \alpha_1 + \alpha_2; \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \beta_2; e^z), \quad z \leq 0
\end{aligned}$$

The proof is concluded ■

2 Moments

PROP. 5 (lemma). Given $X \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta)$ let us consider the random variable $Y = \ln X$. The moments of Y are given by

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad E[Y^n] = (-1)^n \frac{\Gamma(n+1)}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} \frac{(-1)^k}{(\alpha+k)^{n+1}}$$

In particular, for the expectation we have

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad E[Y] = -\frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} \frac{(-1)^k}{(\alpha+k)^2} \cong \ln\left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha+\beta}\right) - \frac{\beta}{2\alpha(\alpha+\beta+1)}$$

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad \text{Var}(Y) \cong \frac{\beta}{\alpha(\alpha+\beta+1)}$$

Proof. For the moments of order n we have

$$\begin{aligned}
E[Y^n] &= \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \int_{-\infty}^0 y^n e^{y\alpha} (1 - e^y)^{\beta-1} dy = \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} (-1)^k \int_{-\infty}^0 y^n e^{y(\alpha+k)} dy = \\
&= \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} (-1)^{k+n+1} \int_{\infty}^0 \xi^n e^{-\xi(\alpha+k)} d\xi = \\
&= \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} (-1)^{n+k} \frac{1}{(\alpha+k)^{n+1}} \int_0^{\infty} (\alpha+k)^n \xi^n e^{-\xi(\alpha+k)} d(\alpha+k)\xi = \\
&= \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} (-1)^{n+k} \frac{1}{(\alpha+k)^{n+1}} \int_0^{\infty} t^{(n+1)-1} e^{-t} dt
\end{aligned}$$

Now we consider that by definition of gamma function, we have $\int_0^{\infty} t^{(n+1)-1} e^{-t} dt = \Gamma(n+1)$, therefore we have found Eq. 7 which gives, in particular, the expectation. We can also employ the well-known result

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad E[Y] \cong \phi(E[X]) + \frac{1}{2} \phi''(E[X]) \text{Var}(X)$$

$$\text{Eq. 11} \quad \text{Var}(Y) \cong (\phi'(E[X]))^2 \text{Var}(X)$$

where $Y = \phi(X)$. In our case we have

$$\phi(x) = \ln(x), \phi'(x) = x^{-1}, \phi''(x) = -x^{-2}, E[X] = \frac{\alpha}{\alpha + \beta}, \text{Var}[X] = \frac{\alpha\beta}{(\alpha + \beta)^2(\alpha + \beta + 1)}$$

Therefore, by substituting these expressions in Eq. 10 and Eq. 11 we find

$$E[Y] \cong \ln\left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + \beta}\right) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\alpha + \beta)^2}{\alpha^2} \frac{\alpha\beta}{(\alpha + \beta + 1)}$$

which corresponds to the left hand of Eq. 8. For the variance we have

$$\text{Var}(Y) \cong (\phi'(E[X]))^2 \text{Var}(X) = \frac{(\alpha + \beta)^2}{\alpha^2} \frac{\alpha\beta}{(\alpha + \beta)^2(\alpha + \beta + 1)} = \frac{\beta}{\alpha(\alpha + \beta + 1)}$$

The exact value of $\text{Var}(Y)$ is $E[Y^2] - E^2[Y]$ and does not seem to be possible a significant simplification of this expression ■

PROP. 6 (moments). It can be shown that

$$\text{Eq. 12} \quad E[Z] = -\frac{1}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_1 - 1}{k} \frac{(-1)^k}{(\alpha_1 + k)^2} + \frac{1}{B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_2 - 1}{k} \frac{(-1)^k}{(\alpha_2 + k)^2}$$

$$\text{Eq. 13} \quad E[Z] \cong \ln\left(\frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_1 + \beta_1} \frac{\alpha_2 + \beta_2}{\alpha_2}\right) - \frac{\beta_1}{2\alpha_1(\alpha_1 + \beta_1 + 1)} - \frac{\beta_2}{2\alpha_2(\alpha_2 + \beta_2 + 1)}$$

$$\text{Eq. 14} \quad \text{Var}[Z] = E[Z^2] - E^2[Z] \cong \frac{\beta_1}{\alpha_1(\alpha_1 + \beta_1 + 1)} + \frac{\beta_2}{\alpha_2(\alpha_2 + \beta_2 + 1)}$$

$$\text{Eq. 15} \quad E[Z^n] = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k E[Y_1^{n-k}] E[Y_2^k]$$

where

$$E[Y_1^{n-k}] = (-1)^{n-k} \frac{\Gamma(n-k+1)}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)} \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_1 - 1}{h} \frac{(-1)^h}{(\alpha_1 + h)^{n-k+1}}$$

$$E[Y_2^k] = (-1)^k \frac{\Gamma(k+1)}{B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_2 - 1}{h} \frac{(-1)^h}{(\alpha_2 + h)^{k+1}}$$

Proof. We make the positions $Z = \ln X_1/X_2 = \ln X_1 - \ln X_2$. Assigned $Y_1 = \ln X_1, Y_2 = \ln X_2$ with Y_1 and Y_2 independent and with $X_1 \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_1, \beta_1)$ and $X_2 \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_2, \beta_2)$ we have $Z = Y_1 - Y_2$. Therefore we can calculate the moment of order n of Z as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} E[Z^n] &= E[(Y_1 - Y_2)^n] = E\left[\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k Y_1^{n-k} Y_2^k\right] = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k E[Y_1^{n-k} Y_2^k] = \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k E[Y_1^{n-k}] E[Y_2^k] \end{aligned}$$

The values of $E[Y_1^{n-k}]$ and $E[Y_2^k]$ can be obtained by applying PROP. 5. For the expectation we have

$$\begin{aligned}
E[Z] &= E[Y_1 - Y_2] = E[Y_1] - E[Y_2] = -\frac{1}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_1 - 1}{k} \frac{(-1)^k}{(\alpha_1 + k)^2} + \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_2 - 1}{k} \frac{(-1)^k}{(\alpha_2 + k)^2} \cong \\
&\cong \ln \left(\frac{\alpha_1(\alpha_1 + \beta_1)}{(\alpha_2 + \beta_2)\alpha_2} \right) - \frac{\beta_1}{2\alpha_1(\alpha_1 + \beta_1 + 1)} + \frac{\beta_2}{2\alpha_2(\alpha_2 + \beta_2 + 1)}
\end{aligned}$$

An approximated expression of the variance can be obtained by substituting Eq. 9 in $Var[Z] = Var[Y_1] + Var[Y_2]$ ■

PROP. 7 (alternative expressions). It can be shown that

$$\text{Eq. 16} \quad E[Z] = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\binom{\beta_1 - 1}{k} (-1)^{k+1} B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + k, \beta_2)}{(\alpha_1 + k)^2} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\binom{\beta_2 - 1}{k} (-1)^k B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + k, \beta_1)}{(\alpha_2 + k)^2}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1) B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)}$$

$$\text{Eq. 17} \quad E[Z] \cong \ln \left(\frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_1 + \beta_1} \frac{\alpha_2 + \beta_2}{\alpha_2} \right) - \frac{\beta_1}{2\alpha_1(\alpha_1 + \beta_1 + 1)} - \frac{\beta_2}{2\alpha_2(\alpha_2 + \beta_2 + 1)}$$

$$\text{Eq. 18} \quad E[Z^n] = \Gamma(n + 1) \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\binom{\beta_1 - 1}{k} (-1)^{k+n} B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + k, \beta_2)}{(\alpha_1 + k)^{n+1}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\binom{\beta_2 - 1}{k} (-1)^k B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + k, \beta_1)}{(\alpha_2 + k)^{n+1}}}{B(\alpha_1, \beta_1) B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)}$$

$$\text{Eq. 19} \quad Var[Z] = E[Z^2] - E^2[Z] \cong \frac{\beta_1}{\alpha_1(\alpha_1 + \beta_1 + 1)} + \frac{\beta_2}{\alpha_2(\alpha_2 + \beta_2 + 1)}$$

Proof. Taking into account the density of PROP. 3 we can calculate the moment of order n as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
E[Z^n] B(\alpha_1, \beta_1) B(\alpha_2, \beta_2) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_1 - 1}{k} (-1)^k B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + k, \beta_2) \int_{-\infty}^0 z^n e^{z(\alpha_1 + k)} dz + \\
&\quad + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta_2 - 1}{k} (-1)^k B(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + k, \beta_1) \int_0^{\infty} z^n e^{-z(\alpha_2 + k)} dz
\end{aligned}$$

Then, we note that

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_{-\infty}^0 z e^{z(\alpha_1 + k)} dz &= \int_{\infty}^0 \xi e^{-\xi(\alpha_1 + k)} d\xi = \frac{-\Gamma(2)}{(\alpha_1 + k)^2} \frac{(\alpha_1 + k)^2}{\Gamma(2)} \int_0^{+\infty} \xi^{2-1} e^{-\xi(\alpha_1 + k)} d\xi = \frac{-1}{(\alpha_1 + k)^2} \\
\int_0^{\infty} z e^{-z(\alpha_2 + k)} dz &= \frac{\Gamma(2)}{(\alpha_2 + k)^2} \frac{(\alpha_2 + k)^2}{\Gamma(2)} \int_0^{\infty} z^{2-1} e^{-z(\alpha_2 + k)} dz = \frac{1}{(\alpha_2 + k)^2}
\end{aligned}$$

And the expression of $E[Z]$ has been proven. For $E[Z^n]$ we operate similarly:

$$\int_{-\infty}^0 z^n e^{z(\alpha_1 + k)} dz = (-1)^{n+1} \int_{+\infty}^0 \xi^{(n+1)-1} e^{-\xi(\alpha_1 + k)} d\xi =$$

$$= (-1)^n \frac{\Gamma(n+1)}{(\alpha_1+k)^{n+1}} \frac{(\alpha_1+k)^{n+1}}{\Gamma(n+1)} \int_0^{+\infty} \xi^{3-1} e^{-\xi(\alpha_1+k)} d\xi = (-1)^n \frac{\Gamma(n+1)}{(\alpha_1+k)^{n+1}}$$

$$\int_0^{+\infty} z^n e^{-z(\alpha_2+k)} dz = \frac{\Gamma(n+1)}{(\alpha_2+k)^{n+1}} \frac{(\alpha_2+k)^{n+1}}{\Gamma(n+1)} \int_0^{+\infty} z^{(n+1)-1} e^{-z(\alpha_2+k)} dz = \frac{\Gamma(n+1)}{(\alpha_2+k)^{n+1}}$$

By substitution of these integrals in $E[Z^n]$ we have the thesis. We can also use the well-known result

Eq. 20 $E[Y] \cong \phi(E[X]) + \frac{1}{2}\phi''(E[X])Var(X)$

Eq. 21 $Var(Y) \cong (\phi'(E[X]))^2 Var(X)$

and we have

$$E[Z] = E[\ln X_1] - E[\ln X_2] \cong \ln\left(\frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_1 + \beta_1} \frac{\alpha_2 + \beta_2}{\alpha_2}\right) - \frac{\beta_1}{2\alpha_1(\alpha_1 + \beta_1 + 1)} - \frac{\beta_2}{2\alpha_2(\alpha_2 + \beta_2 + 1)}$$

$$Var[Y] = Var[\ln X_1] + Var[\ln X_2] \cong \frac{\beta_1}{\alpha_1(\alpha_1 + \beta_1 + 1)} + \frac{\beta_2}{\alpha_2(\alpha_2 + \beta_2 + 1)}$$

And the proof is concluded ■

3 Script

The following Octave script takes as input the parameters of the random variables $X_1 \sim Beta(\alpha_1, \beta_1)$, $X_2 \sim Beta(\alpha_2, \beta_2)$ and it calculates and plots the densities of $\ln X_1$, $\ln X_2^{-1}$, $\ln X_1/X_2$. For the density of $\ln X_1/X_2$ it can call two different subroutines: one implements the summation of Eq. 3 and the other one uses the result of PROP. 4. I report below the main unit and the two subroutines. For the computation of the hypergeometric function, I used the function `gsl_sf_hyperg_2F1()` of the package `gsl`. Figure 1 is an example of the output.

```
% file name = BetaLogHyperGeom
% date of creation = 17/03/2024
%
% Study of Ln(X) and of Ln(-X) when X~B(a,b)
%
clear all
close all
pkg load statistics
pkg load gsl
%
% parameters
%
a1=5;
b1=3;
a2=3;
b2=7;
n=2000; % number o randomly generated numbers
select = 2 % 1 for using the hypergeometric function, 2 for an approximate summation
%
% random generation and histogram
```

```

%
X1=betarnd(a1,b1,1,n);
Y=log(X1);
M=mean(Y);
num_bins = 30;
[counts, bin_centers] = hist(Y, num_bins);
bin_width = bin_centers(2) - bin_centers(1);
%
% analytic density of Y=Ln(X1)
%
len=50;
y=linspace(5*M,0,len);
for i=1:len
    fa(i)=exp(y(i)*a1)*(1-exp(y(i)))^(b1-1);
endfor
fa=fa/beta(a1,b1);
%
% plotting
%
figure
subplot(1,3,1)
bar(bin_centers,counts/(n*bin_width),'FaceColor','yellow','EdgeColor','black','BarWidth',1)
hold on
plot(y,fa,'-k','Linewidth',1)
hold off
title(strcat('density of Y=Ln(X_{1}), X_{1}~Beta(',num2str(a1),',',num2str(b1),')'),'fontsize',15)
xlabel('Ln(X_{1})','fontsize',15)
ylabel('Probability Density','fontsize',15)
%
% histogram and density of Y=Ln(1/X2)
%
X2=betarnd(a2,b2,1,n);
Y=-log(X2);
M=mean(Y);
[counts,bin_centers]=hist(Y,num_bins);
bin_width = bin_centers(2) - bin_centers(1);
%
y=linspace(0,5*M,len);
for i=1:len
    fa(i)=exp(-y(i)*a2)*(1-exp(-y(i)))^(b2-1);
endfor
fa=fa/beta(a2,b2);
%
% plotting
%
subplot(1,3,2)
bar(bin_centers,counts/(n*bin_width),'FaceColor','green','EdgeColor','black','BarWidth',1)
hold on
plot(y,fa,'-k','Linewidth',1)
hold off
title(strcat('density of Y=Ln(1/X_{2}),X_{2}~Beta(',num2str(a2),',',num2str(b2),')'),'fontsize',15)
xlabel('Ln(1/X_{2})','fontsize',15)
ylabel('Probability Density','fontsize',15)
%
% histogram of Y=Ln(X1/X2)
%
Z=log(X1./X2);

```

```

M=mean(Z);
[counts,bin_centers]=hist(Z,num_bins);
bin_width = bin_centers(2) - bin_centers(1);
%
% analytic density of Y=Ln(X1/X2)
%
minimo=min(Z);
massimo=max(Z);
len=50;
z=linspace(minimo,massimo,len);
clear fa
if (select==1)
    for i=1:len
        fa(i)=BetaLogDensityHG(a1,b1,a2,b2,z(i));
    endfor
endif
if (select==2)
    for i=1:len
        fa(i)=BetaLogDensity(a1,b1,a2,b2,z(i));
    endfor
endif
%
% plotting
%
subplot(1,3,3)
bar(bin_centers,counts/(n*bin_width),'FaceColor','blue','EdgeColor','black','BarWidth',1)
hold on
plot(z,fa,'-k','Linewidth',1)
hold off
title(strcat('density of Y=Ln(X_{1}/X_{2})','X_{1}~Beta(',num2str(a1),',',num2str(b1),')',...
',X_{2}~Beta(',num2str(a2),',',num2str(b2),')'),'fontsize',15)
xlabel('Ln(X_{1}/X_{2})','fontsize',15)
ylabel('Probability Density','fontsize',15)

```

```

% file name = BetaLogDensityHG
% date of creation = 17/03/2024
%
% It calculates the density of Y=ln(X1/X2) in z, with
% X1~Beta(a1,b1), X2~Beta(a2,b2). It uses the hypergeometric function.
%
function result = BetaLogDensityHG(a1,b1,a2,b2,z)
    result=0;
    if (z>0)
        result=gsf_sf_hyperg_2F1(1-b2,a1+a2,a1+a2+b1,exp(-z));
        result=exp(-z*a2)*result;
        result=result/beta(a1,b1);
        result=result/beta(a2,b2);
        result=result*beta(a1+a2,b1);
    endif
    if (z<=0)
        result=gsf_sf_hyperg_2F1(1-b1,a1+a2,a1+a2+b2,exp(z));
        result=exp(z*a1)*result;
        result=result/beta(a1,b1);
        result=result/beta(a2,b2);
        result=result*beta(a1+a2,b2);
    endif
end

```

```

% file name = BetaLogDensity
% date of creation = 17/03/2024
%
% It calculates the density of Y=ln(X1/X2) in z, with
% X1~Beta(a1,b1), X2~Beta(a2,b2). It uses a finite summation.
%
function result = BetaLogDensity(a1,b1,a2,b2,z)
    a1=round(a1);
    b1=round(b1);
    a2=round(a2);
    b2=round(b2);
    result=0;
    if (z>0)
        for k=0:(b2-1)
            result = result + nchoosek(b2-1,k)*exp(-k*z)*beta(a1+a2+k,b1)*(-1)^k;
        endfor
        result=exp(-z*a2)*result;
        result=result/beta(a1,b1);
        result=result/beta(a2,b2);
    endif
    if (z<=0)
        for k=0:(b1-1)
            result = result + nchoosek(b1-1,k)*exp(k*z)*beta(a1+a2+k,b2)*(-1)^k;
        endfor
        result=exp(z*a1)*result;
        result=result/beta(a1,b1);
        result=result/beta(a2,b2);
    endif
end
end

```

4 The case of two equal beta laws

If we consider the case of two beta laws with the same parameters, we see from PROP. 3 and PROP. 4 that the density is symmetric with respect to $z = 0$.

PROP. 8 (density). For $\alpha = \alpha_1 = \alpha_2, \beta = \beta_1 = \beta_2$ we have

$$\text{Eq. 22} \quad f_Z(z) = e^{-|z|\alpha} \frac{B(2\alpha, \beta)}{B^2(\alpha, \beta)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} (-1)^k e^{-k|z|} \frac{(2\alpha+k-1)!(2\alpha+\beta-1)!}{(2\alpha-1)!(2\alpha+\beta+k-1)!}$$

$$\text{Eq. 23} \quad f_Z(z) = \frac{e^{-|z|\alpha_2} B(2\alpha, \beta)}{B^2(\alpha, \beta)} F(1-\beta, 2\alpha; 2\alpha+\beta; e^{-|z|})$$

Proof. In this case, from the density in PROP. 3 can be written

$$f_Z(z) = \begin{cases} \frac{e^{-z\alpha}}{B^2(\alpha, \beta)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} (-1)^k e^{-kz} B(2\alpha+k, \beta), & z > 0 \\ \frac{e^{z\alpha}}{B^2(\alpha, \beta)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} (-1)^k e^{kz} B(2\alpha+k, \beta), & z \leq 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 24} \quad f_Z(z) = \frac{e^{-|z|\alpha}}{B^2(\alpha, \beta)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} (-1)^k e^{-k|z|} B(2\alpha+k, \beta)$$

Consider now that from the recursive property of the Gamma function

$$\Gamma(\alpha + n) = \Gamma(\alpha)(\alpha + n - 1)(\alpha + n - 2) \dots \alpha = \Gamma(\alpha) \frac{(\alpha + n - 1)!}{(\alpha - 1)!}$$

and given the relationship $B(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha+\beta)}$ we can write

$$B(2\alpha + k, \beta) = \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha + k)\Gamma(\beta)}{\Gamma(2\alpha + \beta + k)} = \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha) \frac{(2\alpha+k-1)!}{(2\alpha-1)!} \Gamma(\beta)}{\Gamma(2\alpha + \beta) \frac{(2\alpha+\beta+k-1)!}{(2\alpha+\beta-1)!}} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 25} \quad B(2\alpha + k, \beta) = \frac{(2\alpha+k-1)!(2\alpha+\beta-1)!}{(2\alpha-1)!(2\alpha+\beta+k-1)!} B(2\alpha, \beta)$$

By substitution in Eq. 24, we have Eq. 25. On the other hand, Eq. 23 follows immediately from PROP. 4 ■

PROP. 9 (corollary). The second power of the beta function is

$$\text{Eq. 26} \quad B^2(\alpha, \beta) = 2B(2\alpha, \beta) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} \frac{(-1)^k (2\alpha+k-1)!(2\alpha+\beta-1)!}{\alpha+k (2\alpha-1)!(2\alpha+\beta+k-1)!}$$

Proof. Since we know that $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f_Z(z) dz = 1$ we have

$$\frac{1}{2} = \frac{B(2\alpha, \beta)}{B^2(\alpha, \beta)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} (-1)^k \frac{(2\alpha+k-1)!(2\alpha+\beta-1)!}{(2\alpha-1)!(2\alpha+\beta+k-1)!} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-(\alpha+k)z} dz$$

But $\int_0^{+\infty} e^{-(\alpha+k)z} dz = -\frac{1}{\alpha+k} \int_0^{+\infty} d(e^{-(\alpha+k)z}) = -\frac{1}{\alpha+k} (0 - 1) = \frac{1}{\alpha+k}$, therefore we have found

$$\frac{1}{2} = \frac{B(2\alpha, \beta)}{B^2(\alpha, \beta)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} (-1)^k \frac{(2\alpha+k-1)!(2\alpha+\beta-1)!}{(2\alpha-1)!(2\alpha+\beta+k-1)!} \frac{1}{\alpha+k}$$

Which is the thesis ■

What about the moments? From PROP. 7 we find that for n odds $E[Z^n] = 0$:

$$E[Z^n] = \Gamma(n+1) \frac{-\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\binom{\beta-1}{k} (-1)^k B(2\alpha+k, \beta)}{(\alpha+k)^{n+1}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\binom{\beta-1}{k} (-1)^k B(2\alpha+k, \beta)}{(\alpha+k)^{n+1}}}{B^2(\alpha, \beta)} = 0, \quad n \text{ odds}$$

This is in agreement with the fact that the density is symmetric. Let us evaluate the moments for n even:

$$E[Z^n] = 2\Gamma(n+1) \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} \frac{(-1)^k B(2\alpha+k, \beta)}{(\alpha+k)^{n+1}}}{B^2(\alpha, \beta)}, \quad n \text{ even}$$

By substituting Eq. 25 we have

$$\text{Eq. 27} \quad E[Z^n] = \begin{cases} \frac{2\Gamma(n+1)B(2\alpha,\beta)}{B^2(\alpha,\beta)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{k} \frac{(-1)^k}{(\alpha+k)^{n+1}} \frac{(2\alpha+k-1)!(2\alpha+\beta-1)!}{(2\alpha-1)!(2\alpha+\beta+k-1)!}, & n \text{ even} \\ 0, & n \text{ odds} \end{cases}$$

I tried to find a closed formula for $E[Z^n]$ similar to Eq. 26, but I had no success. If we now consider the moments in PROP. 6 instead, we have

$$\text{Eq. 28} \quad E[Z^n] = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k E[Y^{n-k}] E[Y^k]$$

with

$$E[Y^{n-k}] = (-1)^{n-k} \frac{\Gamma(n-k+1)}{B(\alpha,\beta)} \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{h} \frac{(-1)^h}{(\alpha+h)^{n-k+1}}$$

$$E[Y^k] = (-1)^k \frac{\Gamma(k+1)}{B(\alpha,\beta)} \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \binom{\beta-1}{h} \frac{(-1)^h}{(\alpha+h)^{k+1}}$$

The variance can be obtained from Eq. 14:

$$\text{Eq. 29} \quad \text{Var}[Z] \cong 2 \frac{\beta}{\alpha(\alpha+\beta+1)}$$

5 Relative risk

DEF. 1 (relative risk). Given an explanatory variable X that can assume the values $X = 0, 1, \dots, n$ and a dependent binary variable Y , we define *relative risk* each one of the following ratios:

$$\text{Eq. 30} \quad RR_{i,j} = \frac{P(Y=1|X=i)}{P(Y=1|X=j)}, \quad i \neq j$$

If we indicate R_i the number of subjects for which $X = i$ and $Y = 0$ and with S_i the number of individuals described by $X = i, Y = 1$ we can write

$$RR_{1,0} = \frac{P(Y = 1|X = 1)}{P(Y = 1|X = 0)} = \frac{\frac{S_1}{S_1+R_1}}{\frac{S_0}{S_0+R_0}}, \quad RR_{2,0} = \frac{P(Y = 1|X = 2)}{P(Y = 1|X = 0)} = \frac{\frac{S_2}{S_2+R_2}}{\frac{S_0}{S_0+R_0}}, \quad \dots$$

This kind of data is usually displayed in a table like the following one:

	$Y = 0$	$Y = 1$
$X = 0$	R_0	S_0
$X = 1$	R_1	S_1
$X = 2$	R_2	S_2
...

The null hypothesis for $RR_{i,j}$ is that $\frac{S_i}{S_i+R_i} = \frac{S_j}{S_j+R_j}$. According to the central limit theorem in the case of binomial populations, we can associate to $\frac{S_i}{S_i+R_i}$ the law $N(n_i p_i, n_i p_i (1 - p_i))$ where $n_i = S_i + R_i$ and $p_i = \frac{S_i}{S_i+R_i}$. Note now that since $0 \leq p_i \leq 1$, we might be interested in replacing the normal law with a beta one with the same mean and variance and it can be easily found that

$$Beta(p_i(n_i - 1), (1 - p_i)(n_i - 1))$$

is such a density. This means that we can write

$$\text{Eq. 31} \quad RR_{i,j} = \frac{X_i}{X_j}, \quad \begin{cases} X_i \sim Beta(p_i(n_i - 1), (1 - p_i)(n_i - 1)) \\ X_j \sim Beta(p_j(n_j - 1), (1 - p_j)(n_j - 1)) \end{cases}$$

Under the null hypothesis, the law of $RR_{i,j}$ has mean one and therefore is not suited for hypothesis testing. We take the logarithm of $RR_{i,j}$ instead, which under the null hypothesis has a mean of zero. According to Eq. 14, the variance of such a density is given by

$$\text{Var}[\ln(RR_{i,j})] \cong \frac{1 - p_i}{p_i n_i} + \frac{1 - p_j}{p_j n_j} = \frac{1 - \frac{S_i}{S_i+R_i}}{S_i} + \frac{1 - \frac{S_j}{S_j+R_j}}{S_j} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 32} \quad \text{Var}[\ln(RR_{i,j})] \cong \frac{R_i}{S_i(S_i+R_i)} + \frac{R_j}{S_j(S_j+R_j)}$$

Under the null hypothesis ($p_i = p_j = p$) the density of $\ln(RR_{i,j})$ is symmetric with expectance zero and variance $\frac{1-p}{pn_i} + \frac{1-p}{pn_i}$. Not only that but it is also approximated by a centered normal law of the same variance. To show that, we consider the density of PROP. 8 and we make the positions $\alpha = p(n - 1)$, $\beta = (1 - p)(n - 1)$, assuming the size of the two populations is the same. We then plot the density and compare it with $N\left(0, 2 \frac{1-p}{pn}\right)$ for different values of p , as shown in

Figure 2. Density of $\ln(RR_{i,j})$ under the null hypothesis, for two populations of size 41, for values of p equals 0.2, 0.4, 0.6. The density from PROP. 8 (black solid line) is compared with the centered normal density (red dashed line) of the same variance $2 \frac{1-p}{pn}$ and with the histogram of a randomly generated distribution.

All that said, a feasible test for the null hypothesis can be obtained by using the following p value:

$$\text{Eq. 33} \quad p = 2\Phi\left(\frac{-|\ln(RR)|}{\sqrt{\frac{R_1}{S_1(S_1+R_1)} + \frac{R_0}{S_0(S_0+R_0)}}}\right)$$

If it is below a given threshold (usually 0.05), then we say that the null hypothesis is rejected and the relative risk is significantly different from one. Note that a proper demonstration that $\ln(RR)$ is about normal under the null hypothesis would be to compare the moment of the n^{th} order of $\ln(RR)$ as given by Eq. 27 with $\alpha = p(n-1)$, $\beta = (1-p)(n-1)$ and the corresponding moment of $N\left(0, 2\frac{1-p}{pn}\right)$, which is given by $\left(2\frac{1-p}{pn}\right)^{\frac{n}{2}}(n-1)!!$, have a difference that is reasonably small for any value of n ...

6 Script

The following Octave script plots the density of $\ln(RR)$ by assuming $RR = X_1/X_2$ with $X_1, X_2 \sim \text{Beta}(p(n-1), (1-p)(n-1))$ and X_1, X_2 independent. The code compares this density with the histogram of a randomly generated distribution and with the density $N\left(0, \frac{1-p}{pn} + \frac{1-p}{pn}\right)$ for three values of p . It generates Figure 2. It is meant to justify the notion that when the null hypothesis is true the density of $\ln(RR)$ is about normal.

```
% file name = LnRR
% date of creation = 18/03/2024
%
% Study of Ln(X) and of Ln(-X) when X~B(a,b)
%
clear all
close all
pkg load statistics
%
% parameters (positive integers only)
%
p=[0.2,0.4,0.6];
n=41;
n1=n;
n2=n;
N=2000; % number o randomly generated numbers
%
% function for the density of Z=Ln(X1/X2)
%
function result = density(a1,b1,a2,b2,z)
    result=0;
    if (z>0)
        for k=0:(b2-1)
            result = result + nchoosek(b2-1,k)*exp(-k*z)*beta(a1+a2+k,b1)*(-1)^k;
        endfor
        result=exp(-z*a2)*result;
        result=result/beta(a1,b1);
        result=result/beta(a2,b2);
    endif
    if (z<=0)
        for k=0:(b1-1)
```

```

    result = result + nchoosek(b1-1,k)*exp(k*z)*beta(a1+a2+k,b2)*(-1)^k;
endfor
result=exp(z*a1)*result;
result=result/beta(a1,b1);
result=result/beta(a2,b2);
endif
end
%
% function for the density of  $X \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ 
%
function density = normal_density(x, mu, sigma)
    density = (1 / (sqrt(2*pi) * sigma)) * exp(-0.5 * ((x - mu) / sigma).^2);
end
#
# cycle on p
#
figure
for j=1:3
    #
    a1=round(p(j)*(n1-1));
    b1=round((1-p(j))*(n1-1));
    a2=round(p(j)*(n2-1));
    b2=round((1-p(j))*(n2-1));
    %
    % random generation and histogram
    %
    X1=betarnd(a1,b1,1,N);
    X2=betarnd(a2,b2,1,N);
    %
    % histogram of  $Y = \ln(X1/X2)$ 
    %
    Z=log(X1./X2);
    M=mean(Z);
    num_bins=30;
    [counts,bin_centers]=hist(Z,num_bins);
    bin_width = bin_centers(2) - bin_centers(1);
    %
    % analytic density of  $Y = \ln(X1/X2)$ 
    %
    minimo=min(Z);
    massimo=max(Z);
    len=50;
    z=linspace(minimo,massimo,len);
    clear fa
    for i=1:len
        fa(i)=density(a1,b1,a2,b2,z(i));
    endfor
    %
    % analytic density of  $X \sim N(0, \text{Var}[Y])$ 
    %
    VarY=((1-p(j))/p(j))*(n1^-1 + n2^-1);
    fN=normal_density(z,0,sqrt(VarY));
    %
    % plotting
    %
    subplot(1,3,j)
    bar(bin_centers,counts/(N*bin_width),'FaceColor','green','EdgeColor','black','BarWidth',1)

```

```
hold on
plot(z,fa,'-k','Linewidth',1)
hold on
plot(z,fN,'-.r','Linewidth',1.5)
hold off
title(strcat('density of Y=Ln(RR)', 'p = ', num2str(p(j)), ', n = ', num2str(n)), 'fontsize', 15)
xlabel('Ln(X_{1}/X_{2})', 'fontsize', 15)
ylabel('Probability Density', 'fontsize', 15)
endfor
```